

A Study of Ship Rudders with Improved Performances

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Abstract — The maneuverability of a ship in waves is strongly influenced by vessel's inherent course stability and particularly by existing rudder design. The International Maritime Organization (IMO) has published a series of regulations regarding ship maneuverability in adverse conditions at low speed in the range of 4-6 knots. These new higher standard of IMO require new approaches to improve the maneuvering characteristics in waves of the ship comparing with current criteria for calm water.

In the paper, to achieve higher rudder efficiency two technical solutions have been studied - traditional, by increase of rudder area with 20% and innovative – applying the effect of substitution of the trailing edge of the increased rudder design with the wedge tail.

The results of aerodynamic tests performed in BSHC-Varna wind tunnel show a high efficiency in both types than original item, independently of the increased drag. The effect of wedge tail are mostly highlight in the created torque of the rudder, almost double compared to the others. This gives preconditions to analyze the ship energy efficiency of the design point of view.

Keywords — maneuverability, rudder design, wedge tail, aerodynamic tests, torque.

I. INTRODUCTION

Maneuverability is a basic criterion for the ship's characteristics when operating in a restricted area or in seaway. IMO recently turned more attention to the maneuverability of the vessel in seaway and began discussion of introducing additional criterion for ship's characteristics. The current criteria [1] refer to the ideal case - maneuverability in calm water.

In seaway conditions it is necessary to maintain the course with frequently rudder deviations at a relatively low speed. This mode of control has its own disadvantage - the loss of speed caused by the increased resistance of the rudder. This leads to the need to implement rudders with increased lifting force at small angles of deviation and low resistance [5]. Classical variant is the selection of the standard blade, but with enhanced surface - however again would lead to increased resistance. Contemporary approaches are directed to rudders with a variable shape at their rear end - fish tail type, with a back radius of curvature [4, 6].

The article presents the results of the study of variants of rudder types, namely the efficiency of a semi-balanced rudder with a preserved enlarged area and one with its replaced outward edge with a wedge tail. Previous studies have shown that rudders with a large wedge tail, providing significantly higher lifting force, but is accompanied by higher drag. The ideal option would be to determine the dimension of this wedge tail, so as to provide a higher lifting force for small angles of attack but not with higher drag. The possibility of providing the desired lifting force more quickly would result in earlier and effective execution of the specified maneuver.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP AND RUDDERS GEOMETRY

To obtain free-stream rudder characteristics model experiment in BSHC low speed wind tunnel were carried out (Fig.1).

Fig. 1. BSHC low speed wind tunnel

Two variants of the KCS [2] container rudder modification have been selected to provide increased lifting force. The first is the classic approach with increasing its area, in the case of 20%, the second is considered in more detail in recent years and is not yet widespread. It refers to changing the outward edge of the enlarged area blade by replacing it with a wedge tail. The experiments were conducted at attack angles ranging from 0 ° to 35 ° through 5 °, and between 25 ° and 30 ° the step was 1 ° to determine the critical angle of attack.

The main characteristics of the rudders are given in Table 1 [3], and the side view in Fig. 2.

TABLE I. RUDDER MODEL DATA

Parameter	Symbol	Dimension	Basic	Basic + 20%	Basic + 20% + Wedge Tail
Rudder area	A_R	m ²	0.0196	0.02352	0.02352
Rudder movable area	A_{RM}	m ²	0.0163	0.01956	0.01956
Rudder height	h_R	m	0.188	0.188	0.188
Rudder mean chord	b_R	m	0.104	0.122	0.122
Rudder profile	NACA 0018				
Trailing edge thickness		%			0.05 b_R

Fig. 2. Variants of the KCS rudders - type "Mariner"

III. RESULTS OF MEASUREMENTS

The measured forces and moment are processed and presented in the generally accepted dimension of the coefficients, namely:

- Drag coefficient: $C_D = \frac{D}{0,5\rho V^2 S}$
- Lift coefficient: $C_L = \frac{L}{0,5\rho V^2 S}$
- Torque coefficient: $C_N = \frac{N}{0,5\rho V^2 S_x}$

At the small angles of attack - up to 15 °, the difference in drag between the different types of rudders is insignificant - Fig. 3, and in the larger ones - from 20 ° onwards there is a slight increase in the wedge tail. At high angles of deviation, there is a sharp increase in drag to the wedge-tail blade at its critical angle of attack, whereas at the rudder with the enlarged area, the change in its performance in this range of deviation angles is poorly pronounced.

Fig. 3. Drag coefficient comparison

Fig. 4. Lift coefficient comparison

Both modified rudders clearly generate greater lift force in the whole range of angles of deviation - Fig.4. Impresses a feature of the rudder with wedge tail creates clearly noticeable higher lift even at smaller angles of attack of 5° to 15° . With it, there is a steadily higher lifting force and the highest maximum. It also gives little advantage to a later critical angle of attack from the traditional approach with increased rudder area.

The rudder torque is important for the operation of the steering gear and its loading. At small angles of deviation - up to 10° , the moment is very small, and the difference in this indicator for different types of rudders also - Figure 5. At the larger angles of deviation at the rudder with enlarged area, the torque is still small, but in the wedge-tail rudder there is a clear tendency to increase the torque until it is almost doubled. This is due to the large rearward displacement of the application point of the lifting force.

Fig. 5. Torque coefficient comparison

The displacement of the application point of the lift force for all the rudders at the small angles of attack to 15° is very close, about 0.05, as seen in Figure 6. With larger angles, the displacement of the application point with a wedge-tail rudder is much greater than the other, almost double. In this case, the position of the rudder stock would not affect to the efficiency of the steering gear when frequent course adjustments were applied with deviation of the blade to 15° .

Fig. 6 Position of the application point of the lifting force on the chord

Fig. 7. Allowable distance from rudder to propeller

Determining the position of the rudder stock is crucial for the work of the steering machine. Shifting it to avoid loading is a difficult task and unwanted. It should be observed allowable distance 'a' from the rudder's blade to the disc of the propeller, which is regulated by shipping registers and is mainly associated with avoiding high levels of vibration in the stern - Fig. 7.

Fig. 8. Effectiveness of rudder variants

The efficiency criterion for a rudder is expressed by the ratio of the lift force to the drag in function of the angles of the attack - fig.8. When comparing this index about the studied rudders, the increased efficiency of the wedge-tail blade in the range of the minor deviation angles is highlighted, while at the greater angles the efficiency is almost equal.

IV. CONCLUSION

On the basis of the results obtained, it can be concluded that in the range of the small angles of attack, in these rudder modifications the torque created by them and the displacement of their application points of the lifting force are very close. From the standpoint of efficiency of these blades and design point of view it is possible without changing the position of the stock to replace the traditional rudder with increased area with that with a wedge-tail. The second item is much more effective in the range of small angles of deflection applied for frequent adjustments to maintain the course and also equally effective with the first at high angles of attack. This would unload much work of the steering machine – Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Effectiveness of the blade with a wedge-tail against the item with an increased area

Finally, by model experiment or simulation calculations, it is necessary to verify that the selected variant of the control means ensures compliance with the International Maritime Organization's criteria for sufficient maneuverability of the ship [1].

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